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Research Article

**CORRELATION OF HOOKWORM INFECTION & MEAN
CORPUSCULAR HAEMOGLOBIN CONCENTRATION**¹Amna Shabbir, ²Farzeen Fazal, ³Samra Maqbool¹Ex house officer Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur,

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²Doctor in BHU Kamalia, Email: farzeenzenia78@yahoo.com³Doctor in BHU Burewala, Email: samramaqbool313@gmail.com**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:****Objective:** To determine frequency of hookworm infected patients and its relation to mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration**Design & duration:** It is a cross sectional study of observational type completed in six months duration.**Setting:** Study was conducted in peripheral rural areas of city Bahawalpur.**Patients & methods:** People of rural areas in periphery of city Bahawalpur were included in the study using non-probability randomized sampling technique. Blood and stool samples were taken. Blood sample were tested for mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration, and stool samples were tested for hook worm ova to diagnose hook worm infection. Consent was taken from all cases in study group. People irrespective of gender and age were included in this study. Tests were carried out in pathology lab of Bahawal Victoria hospital Bahawalpur. A Performa was designed in which all relevant data was documented like age, gender, hook worm infection and MCHC values as determined from tests.**Results:** Total 800 cases were studied including 214() female and 586() male cases. There were 25.4% cases having hook worm infection and 74.6% were not having infection. There were 10.7% cases having hookworm ova <4000 in stool sample, 6.7% cases were containing ova 4001-8000, 4.1% cases containing 8001-12000 ova and 3.7% cases were containing 12001-16000 ova in stool sample.**Conclusion:** Hookworm infection is much common in people of peripheral areas associated with low mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration.**Key words:** Hookworm infection, MCHC, Anemia**Corresponding author:****Amna Shabbir,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Hookworm infection is a common infection among all parasitic infections.¹ It is mostly prevalent in moist, hot peripheral rural areas associated.^{2,3} It is associated with decrease in mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration and causing anemia in patients.⁴⁻⁶ Hookworm exist in intestines and its ova are excreted through feces. Detection of ova in stool sample confirms its infection.⁷ This infection is common in areas near to river due to humid moist environment, suitable for this infection. This infection is much common in Northern India, Southern Europe, Northern China and Pakistan.⁸ There are evidence that hookworm infection can be imported from tropical area to temperate zone.⁹ In some areas mixed parasitic infections are present. Many recent studies have confirmed hookworm infection is much common in Pakistani rural areas. WHO has emphasized on more research work should be done on prevalence of this infection in Pakistan.¹⁰

PATIENTS & METHODS:

This is a cross sectional study of observational type conducted in peripheral underdeveloped rural areas of city Bahawalpur. Study was started in January and completed after six months duration in June 2020. People of rural areas in periphery of city Bahawalpur were included in the study using non-probability randomized sampling technique. Blood

and stool samples were taken. Blood sample were tested for mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration, and stool samples were tested for hook worm ova to diagnose hook worm infection. Consent was taken from all cases in study group. People irrespective of gender and age were included in this study. Tests were carried out in pathology lab of Bahawal Victoria hospital Bahawalpur. A performa was designed in which all relevant data was documented like age, gender, hook worm infection and MCHC values as determined from tests. SPSS software version 20 and Microsoft office word version 2017 were used. Data was analyzed and results were calculated in the form of percentage, frequency, mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS:

Total 800 cases were studied including 214() female and 586() male cases. There were 25.4% cases having hook worm infection and 74.6% were not having infection. There were 10.7% cases having hookworm ova <4000 in stool sample, 6.7% cases were containing ova 4001-8000, 4.1% cases containing 8001-12000 ova and 3.7% cases were containing 12001-16000 ova in stool sample. Mean age of cases was 32.4±7.5 years. There were 255(31.8%) cases between 10-20 years, 204(25.5%) between 21-30 years, 143(17.8%) between 31-40 years, 108(13.5%) between 41-50 years and 90(11.3%) cases were >50 years of age.

Number of ova in stool sample and its relation with MCHC value (n=203)

Number of ova /gram faeces	Number of subjects (n=203)	Mean MCHC value	P-value	r
<3000	76 (37.4%)	28.43	<0.05	-0.83
3001-6000	68 (33.4%)	26.65		
6001-9000	30 (14.8%)	24.11		
9001-12000	21 (10.3%)	19.32		
12001-15000	8 (3.9%)	16.72		

DISCUSSION:

This study has shown correlation between hookworm infection and MCHC.¹¹ This study is similar to previous studies showing relation between hookworm infection and MCHC, contradicting other studies showing no relation between infection and MCHC.¹²⁻¹⁴ Hookworm infection is a common infection among all parasitic infections. It is mostly prevalent in moist, hot peripheral rural areas associated.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ It is associated with decrease in mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration and causing anemia in patients. Hookworm exist in intestines and its ova are excreted through feces.¹⁸ Detection of ova in stool sample confirms its infection. This infection is common in areas near to river due to humid moist environment, suitable for this infection.¹⁹⁻²¹ This infection is much common in Northern India, Southern Europe, Northern China and Pakistan. This is a cross sectional study of observational type conducted in peripheral underdeveloped rural areas of city Bahawalpur.²²⁻²⁴ Study was started in January and completed after six months duration in June 2020. People of rural areas in periphery of city Bahawalpur were included in the study using non-probability randomized sampling technique. Blood and stool samples were taken. Blood sample were tested for mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration, and stool samples were tested for hook worm ova to diagnose hook worm infection. Consent was taken from all cases in study group. Total 800 cases were studied including 214() female and 586() male cases. There were 25.4% cases having hook worm infection and 74.6% were not having infection. There were 10.7% cases having hookworm ova <4000 in stool sample, 6.7% cases were containing ova 4001-8000, 4.1% cases containing 8001-12000 ova and 3.7% cases were containing 12001-16000 ova in stool sample. In some studies severity of infection was not measured as number of ova in stool sample or methods used

were not accurate as studies done by Kennedy, Old Meadow, Foy and Kondi.²⁵

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